

WHAT ARE THE SYMPTOMS OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY IN MENOPAUSAL WOMEN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14836375>

Relevance of the study: A prospective single-stage clinical study was conducted on 70 women aged 43-57 years (mean age in groups 1 and 2, 48.4 ± 2.2 and 49.1 ± 1.8 years, respectively, without statistically significant differences) in surgical postmenopause lasting from 1 to 5 years. Patients signed voluntary informed consent to participate in the study. All women consulted an obstetrician-gynecologist with complaints of climacteric symptoms of varying severity to decide on the appointment of HRT.

Materials and methods: The study included 70 women aged 43-57 years in surgical postmenopause, which lasted from 1 to 5 years. Before the start of the study, all patients had vitamin D deficiency (less than 20 ng / ml). Depending on the type of HRT prescribed, the patients were divided into 2 groups of 30 people. In group 1, monotherapy with transdermal estrogens was prescribed (17 β -estradiol - gel for external use). In group 2, combined estrogen-progestogen oral MHT (1 mg 17 β -estradiol + 5 mg dydrogesterone) was prescribed. In addition to MHT, all patients received cholecalciferol (vitamin D) at a dose of 6000-8000 IU per day for 8 weeks.

A standard general clinical examination was performed, including biochemical blood tests, lipidogram, phosphorus-calcium metabolism parameters, mammography, pelvic ultrasound, and dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry. All parameters were within reference values, and no statistically significant differences were found between the groups.

Before the study, all patients had vitamin D deficiency (less than 20 ng/ml) and underwent total or subtotal hysterectomy with adjuncts due to combined uterine and ovarian pathology (uterine fibroids and benign ovarian tumors, adenomyosis and benign ovarian tumors).

Research results: against the background of combined MHT, a significant increase in serum vitamin D levels was observed compared to the monotherapy group - with equal doses of drugs and the same initial level of vitamin deficiency.

The prevalence of vitamin D deficiency is 28 to 40% [13]. The importance of vitamin D supplementation is undeniable. It improves calcium and phosphate absorption, thereby promoting musculoskeletal health. Dietary intake is inversely associated with early menopause, but no studies have confirmed a similar risk for plasma 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D] concentrations [8].

According to the literature, a decrease in its level is associated with the development of postmenopausal osteoporosis, but not with the severity or progression of climacteric symptoms.

Several studies have not found a clinically significant relationship between serum 25(OH)D levels and menopausal symptoms in women [9, 10].

Depending on the type of HRT recommended, patients were divided into 2 groups of 30 people. In group 1, women after hysterectomy were prescribed monotherapy with transdermal estrogens (17 β -estradiol - gel for external use). In group 2, combined estrogen-progestogen oral MHT (1 mg 17 β -estradiol + 5 mg dydrogesterone) was recommended in a long-term regimen.

In addition to MHT, all patients were recommended to take oral cholecalciferol (vitamin D). Correction of vitamin D deficiency was performed at a dose of 6000-8000 IU per day for 8 weeks.

Conclusion: The inclusion of a progestogen component in the HRT regimen increases the absorption of vitamin D, and with equal initial values and equal replenishment doses, its level increases more quickly. In this regard, in the presence of a pronounced deficiency of vitamin D, it is recommended to give preference to combined estrogen-progestogen forms of HRT to replenish it more quickly. It is necessary to continue studies in different geographical populations with large samples to identify differences in vitamin D absorption in order to clarify the mechanisms of action of vitamin D in this group of patients and determine a complex therapy regimen for individualized correction.

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